

Microservice API Evolution in Practice: Interview Guide

Background

- Industry field of the company
- Highest relevant education
- Years of experience in software development
- Microservice definition
- Years of experience in microservices architecture
- Current role regarding microservice development
- Team size
- Number of microservices maintained by the team
- Technologies to develop and run the system/cluster (e.g., git, Spring, Kubernetes)

Communication

- How do you implement communication between microservices? Inside your cluster? Outside your cluster?
- How do you expose APIs for your maintained microservices?
 - (ice breaker) Do you expose a REST API for your maintained microservices? If not, what else do you use?
 - How frequently do you use [each technique] to implement microservice communication (%)?
 - How do you document your APIs?

Own API Changes

- How frequently do the APIs of your microservices change (breaking and non-breaking)? Why is it changing so (in-) frequently?
- What are the reasons for the changes?
- How do you manage and implement such changes?
- When and which information (e.g., trigger, change description, contact person, deadline etc) do you communicate to other teams depending on your microservice changes? How internally, how externally?
- How do you know whom to inform? How do you communicate to clients/consumers not known to you?

- Which challenges did you encounter regarding API changes? How often does it happen?
- How could your process for implementing and advertising changes be improved?
- What would you need to improve the process?

External API Changes

- How many externally managed microservices/systems do you depend on, approximately?
- How frequently do the external APIs change?
- How do you learn about changes in the microservices you consume?
- How do you identify if the changes are relevant for your microservices?
- How do you integrate such changes? How long does it take to integrate such changes into your microservice(s)?
- Which challenges did you encounter regarding integrating API changes? How often do they happen?
- How could your process for integrating external changes be improved?
- What would you need to improve the process?

Outlook

- Do you have additional thoughts you want to express?